

PEDAGOGICAL SCIENCES

RESEARCH ON CURRICULUM INTEGRATION AND TEACHING REFORM OF ADVANCED ALGEBRA AND ANALYTIC GEOMETRY FOR THE MAJOR OF INFORMATION AND COMPUTING SCIENCE

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Abstract

Based on the talent training objectives of the Information and Computing Science major, this paper analyzes the current status and core problems of curriculum teaching, constructs a curriculum integration system adapted to professional needs, innovates teaching methods and practical teaching modes, and optimizes the assessment and evaluation mechanism. Through a series of teaching reform explorations, it aims to solve the problems of disconnection between courses and the major, and separation of theory from practice, improve the quality of curriculum teaching and students' mathematical application ability, and provide reference for the reform of basic mathematics courses in the Information and Computing Science major and similar interdisciplinary majors.

Keywords: Information and Computing Science; Advanced Algebra; Analytic Geometry; Teaching Reform; Curriculum Integration.

1 Introduction

As an interdisciplinary and integrated major combining mathematics and computer science, Information and Computing Science has a core training objective: cultivating high-quality talents with a solid mathematical foundation and strong computer application capabilities, who can engage in scientific research and application work in fields such as data analysis, numerical computation, algorithm design, and artificial intelligence. As two core basic mathematical courses for this major, Advanced Algebra and Analytic Geometry shoulder the key mission of building theoretical frameworks, fostering mathematical thinking, and providing professional tools.

With the rapid iteration of emerging technologies such as big data, artificial intelligence, and digital twins, industries have put forward higher requirements for the mathematical application capabilities of talents in the Information and Computing Science major [1]. In the current teaching practice of most universities, Advanced Algebra and Analytic Geometry still adopt the traditional teaching mode, which has problems including the disconnection between curriculum positioning and professional needs, weakened correlation between the two courses, overemphasis on theoretical derivation in teaching content, and a single teaching method. These issues lead to students generally reflecting that the courses are abstract and difficult to understand, resulting in insufficient learning interest and difficulty in effectively transferring the learned knowledge to subsequent professional studies and practical work. The traditional teaching mode can no longer meet the needs of professional talent training in the new era [2].

A review of relevant research results at home and abroad reveals that the teaching reform of Advanced Algebra and Analytic Geometry has become one of the hot topics in the research of basic mathematics courses. Domestic studies mostly focus on the optimization of teaching methods for a single course (such as the application of case-based teaching and online-offline

blended teaching) or preliminary attempts at integrating the two courses [3]. However, most studies still remain at the level of simple deletion and splicing of knowledge points, failing to fully combine the interdisciplinary characteristics of the Information and Computing Science major to construct a deeply integrated curriculum system, and insufficient attention is paid to the connection between practical teaching and professional application. Relevant foreign majors (such as Computational Mathematics in the United States and Mathematics and Computing in the United Kingdom) pay more attention to the application-oriented orientation of basic mathematics courses. Through project-based learning, integration of interdisciplinary cases, and in-depth application of mathematical software, they realize the organic combination of mathematical theory and professional practice. Their teaching philosophy emphasizing "knowledge application" and "competency development" provides valuable reference for domestic teaching reform, but foreign models need to be localized according to the teaching resources and students' learning conditions of domestic universities.

Based on this, grounded in the talent cultivation objectives of the Information and Computing Science major, this paper takes Advanced Algebra and Analytic Geometry as the research objects. It systematically sorts out domestic and foreign teaching reform experiences through the literature research method, investigates the teaching pain points of teachers and students using the questionnaire survey method and interview method, and conducts teaching practice verification by applying the case study method and comparative analysis method. The core research contents include: analyzing the current status and core problems of curriculum teaching, constructing a curriculum integration system adapted to professional needs, innovating teaching methods and practical teaching models, and optimizing the assessment and evaluation mechanism. Through a series of teaching reform explorations, this study aims to solve the problems of disconnection between courses and the major as well as separation of

theory from practice, improve the quality of curriculum teaching and students' mathematical application capabilities, and provide reference for the reform of basic mathematics courses in the Information and Computing Science major and similar interdisciplinary majors.

2 Current Status and Problem Analysis of Advanced Algebra and Analytic Geometry Teaching for the Information and Computing Science Major

2.1 Current Teaching Status

As core foundational courses for the Information and Computing Science major, Advanced Algebra and Analytic Geometry provide key theoretical support for subsequent courses such as Numerical Analysis and Machine Learning. Currently, teaching is mainly based on classroom lectures, with some universities integrating online resources for auxiliary teaching, but the setup of practical links is generally weak. Students' classroom participation varies greatly, the quality of homework completion shows a two-way split, exam scores are concentrated on basic knowledge points, and scores on comprehensive application questions are relatively low.

2.2 Analysis of Existing Problems

(1) In Terms of Curriculum Content

The courses are dense with abstract concepts and complex theoretical derivations, making it difficult for students to understand and establish rapid knowledge connections. The internal logical connection between the two courses is insufficient, the idea of combining numbers and shapes has not been fully infiltrated, and the teaching presents a state of "operating independently".

(2) In Terms of Teaching Methods

Traditional lecture-based teaching dominates, where students passively receive knowledge and lack space for active exploration and interactive communication. Practical teaching resources are scarce, and there is a lack of professional-related application scenario design, making it difficult for students to transform theory into practice.

(3) In Terms of Students' Learning

The difficulty and abstractness of the courses are likely to make students feel intimidated, directly affecting their learning initiative and self-confidence. Most students lack systematic learning methods, struggle to construct a complete knowledge system, and have weak knowledge transfer capabilities.

(4) In Terms of Assessment Methods

Assessment is mainly based on closed-book exams, focusing on the memory of theoretical knowledge and basic problem-solving skills, while neglecting the evaluation of practical abilities and innovative thinking. The proportion of process-oriented assessment is relatively low, failing to fully reflect students' learning processes and comprehensive qualities.

3 Curriculum Integration and Content Optimization of Advanced Algebra and Analytic Geometry for the Information and Computing Science Major

3.1 Core Principles of Curriculum Integration

Relevance Principle: Based on the internal logic of the two courses (such as the connection between matrices and spatial geometry, linear transformations and coordinate transformations), realize the organic integration of the knowledge system.

Professional Adaptation Principle: Centering on the core competence requirements of the Information and Computing Science major, screen and reconstruct teaching content to strengthen the application orientation.

Progressive Principle: Follow students' cognitive rules, and gradually construct the knowledge system from basic theories to applied practices, and from simplicity to complexity.

3.2 Curriculum Content Integration

(1) In the basic module, integrate core theoretical knowledge and eliminate redundant content. It includes vectors and vector spaces (integrating geometric intuition with algebraic expression), matrices and determinants (linking linear transformations in geometry), linear equations and linear transformations (combining geometric application scenarios), and quadratic forms and quadric surfaces (connecting algebraic operations with geometric figure analysis).

(2) In the professional application module, supplement professional-related application content. Examples include fundamentals of numerical linear algebra (matrix decomposition, application of iterative methods in numerical computation), geometric modeling and graphics processing (application of analytic geometry in computer graphics), and linear algebra tools in data analysis (mathematical principles of principal component analysis and linear regression).

(3) In the expansion module, introduce cutting-edge interdisciplinary content. For instance, linear algebra foundations in machine learning (application of vector spaces and matrix operations in algorithms), matrix optimization methods in big data processing, etc., to broaden students' horizons.

3.3 Teaching Content Optimization Strategies

(1) Reduce the difficulty of pure theoretical proofs, and help students understand abstract concepts through geometric figures and practical examples (such as explaining linear correlation with the geometric meaning of spatial vectors).

(2) Embed specific professional cases in the explanation of knowledge points, such as using matrix operations to process image data and linear transformations to achieve dimensionality reduction, reflecting the combination of mathematics and the major.

(3) Based on the integrated framework, compile textbooks or handouts that meet the needs of the Information and Computing Science major, and supplement application cases and practical exercises.

4 Innovation of Teaching Methods and Means for Advanced Algebra and Analytic Geometry in the Information and Computing Science Major

4.1 Optimizing Teaching Content

Students majoring in Information and Computing Science need to master the basic ideas, core content, and fundamental skills of Advanced Algebra and Analytic Geometry. However, there should be certain distinctions from the training of mathematics teacher candidates. For this major, it is not necessary to prove every theorem and corollary. To ensure the systematicness of knowledge and achieve the training objectives, essential proofs cannot be omitted either. Teachers need to boldly and flexibly optimize the content in teaching, formulate a curriculum syllabus suitable for

the major, briefly cover or even omit some content, while frequently summarizing knowledge to maintain a clear teaching thread.

Currently, there is no single textbook on Advanced Algebra and Analytic Geometry that is fully suitable for this major. Common textbooks include *Advanced Algebra and Analytic Geometry* [4] by Professor Chen Zhijie and *Advanced Algebra and Analytic Geometry* [5] by Professor Meng Daoji—both excellent works that only require content optimization based on actual needs. Some students find specialized textbooks too difficult and use Linear Algebra or Linear Algebra and Spatial Geometry as reference books. They believe this approach facilitates understanding, helps construct knowledge frameworks, and can be regarded as a viable method.

4.2 Rational Application of Modern Teaching Technology

The Information and Computing Science major aims to cultivate students with strong data processing capabilities and has high requirements for their ability to apply mathematical software. Therefore, it is necessary to consciously cultivate students' ability to use mathematical software to solve mathematical problems starting from basic courses. For example, some calculations can be implemented through Matlab, and other software can also be used. On the one hand, this allows students to understand the close connection between mathematics and computers and the characteristics of the major at an early stage; on the other hand, it can stimulate students' learning enthusiasm.

Some calculations are cumbersome and abstract, which may fail to arouse students' interest, such as determinant calculations, matrix calculations, solution of linear equations, quadratic forms and similar matrices, and eigenvalue calculations. After conducting necessary proofs and method introductions, using computer software to assist in demonstrating the solution process when explaining examples can improve students' enthusiasm. It is also conducive for students to understand the professional characteristics, preventing them from still not knowing the differences between this major and the mathematics teacher training major by the second semester of their sophomore year.

By introducing software such as Mathematica, Matlab, and Python, we can realize the visualization of mathematical concepts (e.g., dynamic demonstration of linear transformations) and the automation of complex calculations, thereby enhancing the intuitiveness and efficiency of teaching. Utilize multimedia and visualization tools like PPT, animations, and 3D modeling software to convert abstract mathematical concepts (such as high-dimensional spaces and quadric surfaces) into intuitive images, assisting students in understanding. Leverage online interactive platforms including Rain Classroom and Superstar Learning to conduct real-time interactions, push exercises, and address questions, strengthening teacher-student interaction and learning feedback.

4.3 Infiltrating Mathematical Modeling Ideas and Highlighting Application Characteristics

As an application-oriented major, Information and Computing Science requires students to have strong abilities in applying mathematics to solve problems.

Mathematical modeling is precisely an excellent way to cultivate this ability [6]. Although Advanced Algebra and Analytic Geometry may seem loosely connected to practical problems, as a foundational course, many of its theorems, corollaries, and examples embody modeling ideas.

Teachers only need to adopt problem-driven teaching, appropriately encourage and guide students to explore actively, structure and program abstract theorems and formulas, and enhance students' mathematical thinking. Specifically, this can be infiltrated in the proof of theorems, derivation of formulas, and explanation of examples—extracting mathematical models from general scenarios and encouraging students to think independently.

This kind of infiltration does not mean solving a specific practical problem. Moreover, the knowledge students have learned so far is insufficient to tackle more complex practical issues, which is the task of specialized mathematical modeling courses. Instead, Advanced Algebra and Analytic Geometry should focus on subtly infiltrating modeling ideas in class to cultivate students' model-based thinking.

5 Reform of the Assessment and Evaluation System

5.1 Transformation of Assessment and Evaluation Concepts

Shift from "emphasizing theory and results" to "valuing abilities and processes", and construct a comprehensive and diversified assessment and evaluation system to fully reflect students' learning effects and comprehensive abilities.

5.2 Optimization of Assessment and Evaluation Content

Theoretical Knowledge Assessment: Focus on examining students' understanding and flexible application of core concepts and basic principles, and reduce questions that require rote memorization.

Practical Ability Assessment: Increase practical assessment content such as experimental operations, project design, and case analysis to examine students' hands-on skills and knowledge application capabilities.

Innovation Ability Assessment: Set open-ended questions and innovative projects to encourage students to propose unique solutions and methods, and assess their innovative thinking.

5.3 Diversification of Assessment and Evaluation Methods

Formative Assessment (Accounting for 40%-50%): Including classroom performance, online learning progress, homework completion quality, experimental reports, group discussion participation, and curriculum design, it comprehensively tracks students' learning processes.

Summative Assessment (Accounting for 50%-60%): Adopt the closed-book exam format, focusing on the application of theories.

Supplementary Assessment: Award extra points to students who participate in academic competitions, research projects, or publish relevant papers to encourage students to take the initiative to expand their learning.

5.4 Refinement of Assessment and Evaluation Criteria

Formulate clear scoring guidelines, quantify the assessment key points and scoring standards for each link such as theoretical answers and project design, so as to ensure the fairness and impartiality of the assessment.

6 Conclusion

Although this research has achieved the expected results, there are still certain limitations: first, the pilot scope and sample size of the teaching reform are limited, and the universality of the results needs to be verified in a wider range of teaching practices; second, the reform practice cycle is one semester, and the long-term teaching effects and the sustainability of students' knowledge transfer need further tracking; third, the teaching implementation of some cutting-edge extended content has high requirements for teachers' professional capabilities, making it difficult to promote in colleges and universities with limited teaching resources.

In the future, further research and practice can be carried out from three aspects: first, expand the pilot scope, optimize the adaptability of the reform plan in combination with the teaching resources and student characteristics of different types of colleges and universities, and form a hierarchical and classified teaching guidance system; second, continuously update the course content, closely track the development of emerging fields such as artificial intelligence and digital twins, dynamically supplement cutting-edge mathematical application cases, and strengthen the timeliness and forward-looking of the course; third, strengthen the

construction of the teaching staff, improve teachers' interdisciplinary integration capabilities and practical teaching levels through school-enterprise cooperation, teaching and research training, etc., and promote the co-construction and sharing of digital teaching resources to provide guarantee for the continuous deepening of the reform and help steadily improve the talent training quality of the Information and Computing Science major.

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